

THE CHALLENGE OF PREDICTING FAILURE IN COMPOSITES

M. R. Wisnom

Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science

University of Bristol, Bristol, United Kingdom

M.Wisnom@bristol.ac.uk

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The failure process in composites is very complex, with multiple different mechanisms that may interact, making predicting failure extremely challenging. There is a shortage of really good experimental data, and after 50 years of research, the issue of failure criteria is still unresolved despite huge efforts on programmes such as the World Wide Failure Exercises [1,2].

A first challenge is to define what is meant by failure. Matrix cracking typically occurs quite early and is sometimes referred to as first ply failure, yet may have little effect on load carrying ability. In fact splitting allows stress redistribution at features such as notches, and may actually increase the ultimate strength. On the other hand some specimens may show no evidence of visible damage or load drops during testing, yet be found to contain substantial damage when examined in detail for example using X-ray CT scans.

The difficulty of obtaining good experimental data can be illustrated by the most basic of all tests, to determine the unidirectional fibre direction strength. Straight-sided specimens with constant cross-section are normally used, yet these contain significant stress concentrations where they are gripped and loaded in addition to localised through thickness compressive and shear stresses [3]. Failure therefore usually occurs prematurely at these points. Careful preparation of tensile specimens with very gradually chamfered thickness can lead to significantly higher failure stresses [4, 5]. If failure does occur in the gauge section despite the stress concentrations, there must be some defect or other factor responsible. For example quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy specimens failing in the gauge section were found to have lower ultimate

strains compared to the unidirectional material, due to failure initiating as a result of delamination at the free edge [5].

Such premature failures can also mask the size effect, whereby larger specimens tend to fail at lower stresses than smaller ones. This affects most failure modes in composites due to the brittle nature of fracture that depends on critical defects, which tend to increase in severity with increasing volume of material under stress [6]. For example in very carefully chamfered unidirectional specimens a 14% reduction in tensile strength (defined as the point of catastrophic failure) was found going from specimens of size 0.5 x 5 x 30 mm to 4 x 40 x 240 mm [5].

Another key challenge is that fracture often occurs due to the effect of multiple discrete cracks joining up to form a failure surface [7]. Whilst a single matrix crack may have negligible effect on overall strength, if several cracks can join up via delaminations, the specimen may be able to shed load completely without any fibres breaking. For example a $(\theta/-\theta)_s$ laminate can separate into two pieces by pull-out as a result of three matrix cracks linked by delaminations at the two $\pm\theta$ interfaces. This mechanism however relies on free edges being present, and the response of unnotched tubular specimens with the same layup may be completely different.

The way in which such discrete cracks interact can produce very large differences in failure stresses and modes. For example in unnotched $(45_m/90_m/-45_m/0_m)_{ns}$ carbon/epoxy laminates the tensile strength varied by a factor of almost 3 for different values of m and n [5]. Conventional failure criteria

would predict the same strength in all cases, illustrating the limitation of treating the composite as a homogenised material.

The effect of defects is also extremely important. Factors such as fibre waviness can cause large reductions in strength. These also depend on the manufacturing process, and so it is crucial that test specimens are representative of the actual as-manufactured structure. There are also intrinsic features in composites that have similar effects to defects. For example ply terminations act as local stress concentrations that can initiate delamination and lead to premature fibre failure.

Failure is very a complex process, governed by many other factors beyond the simple multi-axial stress state, including the ply thickness, stressed volume, free edges, ply drops, and defects arising in manufacturing or service. It is therefore not surprising that there are difficulties in applying simple failure criteria. These can never the less be very useful in design of structures, but should perhaps be referred to as design criteria rather than failure criteria. The key issue is to understand their limitations and range of validity. The effect of delamination is particularly important. This is usually associated with out-of-plane loading, but can also have a large effect on in-plane strength [8].

A similar issue arises with approaches such as the average failure stress criterion, which is widely used to assess the importance of stress concentrations. For example it has been applied to the case of open hole tensile and compressive strength [9]. Reasonably good results were obtained for dispersed layups where failure was fibre dominated, but in cases with blocked plies, delamination occurred at much lower stresses. It is therefore critical to understand when the criterion breaks down. In this specific case, this happened mainly due to delamination at ply thicknesses of 0.5 mm or greater, but it also depends on the specimen geometry, and on the material, especially the interlaminar fracture toughness.

To accurately predict failure, the physical controlling mechanisms need to be taken into account, which may be different in different cases. Detailed models are required, which include the

critical phenomena at the appropriate level. When this approach is adopted, good predictions can be obtained, for example for failure of tapered composites with ply drops [10] and at stress concentrations such as open holes [11], opening the way for effective virtual testing of composites.

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